

STEADY STATE THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY MEASUREMENT AT MICROSCALE

S. Ganguli⁽¹⁾, A. Roy⁽²⁾, R. Wheeler⁽³⁾, L. Starman⁽⁴⁾

(1) University of Dayton Research Institute

300 College Park, Dayton, OH 45469-0168, USA Sabyasachi.ganaguli@wpafb.af.mil

(2) Corresponding author, Air Force Research Laboratory

AFRL/RXBT, 2941 Hobson Way, Wright-Patterson AFB, OH 45433-7750, USA

ajit.roy@wpafb.af.mil

(3) UES, 4401 Dayton-Xenia Dr., Dayton, OH 45432-1894

Robert.wheeler@wpafb.af.mil

(4) Air Force Institute of Technology, Wright-Patterson AFB, OH 45433

levarn.starman@afit.edu

SUMMARY

The thermal transport in heterogeneous materials system is critically influence by the phonon scattering at the materials interface. Thermal property measurement at the micron scale is essentially needed for experimental validation of thermal transport mechanism at the vicinity of the materials interface, and to aid the materials interface design. In this work, the RTD (Resistance Temperature Detector) thermal measurement concept is used to develop a micron scale steady state temperature measurement technique for measuring thermal conductivity. MEMS-based micro heater design and configuration of the micro heaters and RTDs for thermal conductivity measurement in an environmental SEM is discussed. The calibration of the RTDs is presented.

Keywords: Thermal materials, Resistance Temperature Detector, Thermal conductivity measurement, Micro heater, Thermal interface

INTRODUCTION

As more high power density electronics are integrated in modern aerospace systems, thermal management of these systems has become a critical research area to promote further development in this area. Further miniaturization of electronic circuits has exasperated localized heating problems. Thus, development of superior thermally conductive materials is a key component in development of modern aerospace systems. The thermal interface design is extremely important in tailoring the thermal materials performance, especially in heterogeneous materials system. Recently, there are increased interests and on-going efforts in the molecular scale materials design for thermal materials, a nicely reviewed by Cahill, et al [1]. One of the big challenges however is to quantify the thermal energy transport at the micron scale, as needed for model validation and hence to aid materials design. Numerous researches in this area involve understanding the thermal transport properties of the microscale/nanoscale constituents in these new materials [2-4]. Besides these efforts, the development of steady state and transient characterization of thermal transport in the thermal devices

and systems is important for performance analysis and tailoring its thermal performance.

A number of attempts have been made to determine the thermal transport properties of microscale structures ranging from micro thermocouples, infrared thermography, scanning thermal microscopy, thermoreflectance microscopy, picosecond laser pump probe technique to Raman spectroscopy [1, 3-8]. Christofferson et al., in a review article summarizes these different techniques and discusses the advantages and disadvantages of these different techniques [2]. The limitation of all these above mentioned techniques is that they do not give direct measurement of the thermal conductivity. Further, they involve either complicated sample preparation or very sophisticated and difficult data analysis and interpretation techniques.

In this study, we propose an intuitively simple steady state microscale thermal conductivity measurement technique. The technique involves a heat source and a heat sink. The sample is to be placed in between the heat source and the sink. The temperature measurement devices (platinum resistance temperature devices) are placed on the heater, sample, and sink to accurately measure the temperatures. The thermal conductivity, k , is known as the property of a material that indicates its ability to conduct heat. It appears primarily in Fourier's Law for heat conduction and is defined by the formula,

$$H = \frac{\Delta Q}{\Delta t} = k \times A \times \frac{\Delta T}{x} \quad (1)$$

where $\frac{\Delta Q}{\Delta t}$ is the rate of heat flow, k is the thermal conductivity, A is the total cross sectional area of conducting surface, ΔT is temperature difference and x is the thickness of conducting surface separating the two temperatures.

A schematic of the proposed system is shown if Figure 1.

Figure 1. Schematic of the microscale thermal conductivity technique is shown.

Thus, rearranging the equation gives thermal conductivity,

$$k = \frac{\Delta Q}{\Delta t} \times \frac{1}{A} \times \frac{x}{\Delta T} \quad (2)$$

In Eq (2) above, the accuracy of determining the value of the thermal conductivity, k , greatly depend on the measurement resolution of the heat flux, $\Delta Q/\Delta t$, and the temperature difference, ΔT , across the specimen length. The heat flux can reliably determine for the resistance of the heating elements and the input electric power. In developing the measurement technique, the temperature drop measurement across the specimen length is thus of high importance in this study.

DEVELOPMENT OF MICRON SCALE THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY MEASUREMENT TECHNIQUE

The technique involves design and development of microheaters with built in temperature measurement devices. A schematic of the first generation devices is shown in Figure 2. The red and blue lines are for the thermocouples. The device consists of two sets of heater thermocouples. The first heater is has wider lines of ~15 micrometer line width while the fine heater has a line width of ~2 micrometers. The heaters and thermocouples were photolithographed and then sputtered on a Sapphire wager 500 micrometer thick. The impedance of the first heater is about 1 k-ohms while that for the fine heater is around 5 k-ohms. The fine heater was incorporated in the system to provide finer control on the heat. Typically the sample would be placed in between the two heaters by a nanomanipulator. The experiment was performed inside a SEM with chamber pressure around 1E-06 torr. The chip was packaged in a conventional ceramic package as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 2. Schematic of the chip design for two adjacent microheaters/thermocouples configured for test frame is shown.

Figure 3. Shown above is the schematic of the packaged and wire bonded microheater/thermocouple chip for the experimental set up.

The leads for the heater and thermocouples were then connected to a Keithley S4200 semiconductor testing system for supplying current and measuring the change in resistance. After initial runs the design was changed to incorporate Platinum RTDs in place of the Au/Pt thermocouples as the Au wire bonding was cancelling off any emf's being generated due to temperature changes. The platinum RTDs were calibrated at different temperatures. A setup for the calibration of the RTDs with reference to calibrated thermocouples is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Set for the calibration of the Platinum RTD with known calibrated thermocouples is shown above.

In order to calibrate the thermocouple, to assess its temperature measurement accuracy, two micro heaters with RTDs were placed in an environmental SEM and were subjected to a controlled heating cycle. The temperature response plots of the RTD's are shown in Figure 5. We observe that that both the RTDs' respond almost identically, which implies good reliability and accuracy of the RTDs electrical resistance response to temperature. Next a sample was attached in the system for testing, but a very small

temperature discrepancy of $\sim 1^\circ\text{C}$ was measured. This small temperature difference was attributed mainly to the huge thermal mass (~ 500 micrometer sapphire substrate). From the results of the initial design, we decided to redesign the device with an objective to reduce the thermal mass. In the new design, the substrate will be reactive ion etched to reduce the thermal mass. The heater lines and the RTD lines would be on trenches. This should improve the thermal response behavior of the whole device. A schematic of the new design is shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Calibration of two RTDs in an environmental SEM is shown. Recorded resistance change of the two RTDs exposed to a heating cycle in an SEM is shown. There is good agreement of the resistance change between the two RTDs subjected to the temperature change, implying good reliability of the measurement technique.

CONCLUSIONS

The development of a micron scale steady state thermal conductivity measurement technique is presented. The measurement is based on a MEMS-based micro heater design with embedded thermocouple (RTD) in the chip design. The electrical resistance measurement of the RTDs in a environmental SEM indicate good accuracy of the measurement technique. However, our initial design of the micro heater chip needs to be modified to reduce the thermal mass of the chip substrate. A modified design with reduced thermal mass is being fabricated and will be tested next.

Figure 6. The new design with reduced thermal mass with heater lines on trenches.

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